

Cyber Sentry: A Chatbot Solution for Tackling Cybercrime

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ABSTRACT: Cybercrime is becoming an increasingly widespread issue in India, leaving individuals struggling to navigate the complex legal system surrounding these violations. To address this problem, a Cyber Crime Chatbot Generator for Indian Law has been developed. This innovative technology aims to bridge the legal knowledge gap by providing an easy-to-use, readily accessible educational resource for dealing with cybercrime-related problems. The chatbot generator is built on a robust platform that provides detailed guidance on recognizing, understanding, and addressing cybercrime concerns under Indian legislation. The system promotes transparency and trust in the legal system by providing a wealth of legal resources, articles, and frequently asked questions on cybercrime to enhance users' knowledge and understanding. In addition to empowering individuals, this innovative approach aims to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of India's legal system in combating cybercrime and promote a more equitable and knowledgeable society. The Cyber Crime Chatbot Generator for Indian Law is poised to have a significant impact on the fight against cybercrime in India by utilizing technology to bridge the legal knowledge gap.

Keywords: Cybercrime, Legal System, Chatbot, Resource, Legal knowledge.

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era of boundary-breaking legal assistance, a visionary initiative arises, offering empowerment and reshaping the legal landscape. Legal understanding becomes universally accessible, transcending the confines of attorney offices. This interactive platform offers pre-emptive solutions, addressing users' needs before formal consultations. Its core philosophy lies in empowering individuals with legal knowledge for confident decision-making. The multifaceted design caters to various services, from common legal queries to guiding initial legal steps, fostering legal literacy and societal participation. Beyond traditional challenges, the platform addresses cybercrime, offering guidance on online fraud, data breaches, and

identity theft. It prioritizes educating users on cybersecurity best practices, aiming to prevent future incidents. Technologically advanced, it utilizes natural language processing and machine learning to provide accurate and dynamic legal advice. Real-time risk assessments guide users on the urgency of actions, streamlining decision-making. Privacy and confidentiality are paramount, with robust encryption and protective measures ensuring user data security. This initiative isn't static; it's a dynamic system adapting to legal and cyber challenges. Leveraging technology, it offers proactive and responsive tools, empowering individuals to navigate complexities with confidence and efficacy.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 LawBot:

LawBot is designed and implemented to provide functionality for facilitating legal research over the Internet. Legal research involves the process of locating and organizing a collection of legal documents, including constitutional provisions, statutes, and cases relevant to the matter in question.

LawBot is implemented as a set of agents that operate according to the user's preferences to gather, filter, organize, and recommend pertinent case histories, state statutes, or supreme court cases. Recognizing the need to simplify research for the public, LawBot has integrated a novel ontology-based search feature. This ontology maps colloquial terms to corresponding legal terminology, enhancing query refinement by searching related words to yield a more comprehensive document set.

2.1.1 LawBot Architecture:

The system architecture comprises the following modules:

- **Interface:** The interface serves to connect with the user preference database, gather user interactions, forward user queries to the resource managers, and display results provided by the resource manager to the user.
- **Resource Manager:** This module is responsible for organizing, retrieving, and processing information. It interprets user queries by consulting domain ontologies and deploys the relevant resource agents as needed.
- **Resource Agent:** Resource agents are programmed to access specific web-based sites based on the user's jurisdiction selection. Retrieved documents undergo word filtering
- and are sorted by relevance. These ordered documents are then sent back to the resource manager using Agent Communication Language (ACL).
- **LawBot Database:** This database stores user preferences, domain ontology, and auxiliary information, such as frequently used links.
- **Proactive Component:** The proactive component uses stored user preferences and past queries to conduct more extensive offline research when the user is not logged in. If new, highly relevant documents are found in this offline search, the user receives notifications about the availability of new documents pertinent to their interests.

2.2 LIRFSS:

In the framework of LIRFSS (Legal Information Retrieval and Focused Semantic Search), the system exclusively focuses on domain-specific legal judgments originating from the Supreme Court of India. These judgments, pertaining specifically to criminal murder cases, are sourced from the Supreme Court's online repository accessible at <http://judis.nic.in/supremecourt/chejudis.asp>

2.2.1 Information Extraction (IE):

Information Extraction (IE) is the process of deriving organized data from unstructured text. In this scenario, IE is applied to a collection of criminal murder case judgments. It involves annotating the documents to extract specific details like the date, location of the incident, and pertinent Indian Penal Code (IPC) sections, transforming raw text into structured information.

2.2.2 LIRFSS System Architecture:

- Online Stored Legal Data: Judgments are collected in PDF format. These judgments contain metadata, including petitioner names, respondent names, judgment dates, names of judges involved in the case, dates, locations of the crime, relevant IPC sections, and the judgment itself.
- Information Retrieval: The initial phase of the system involves basic annotations across the corpus. Various processing modules, including ANNIE, are used for named entity recognition. ANNIE encompasses resources like Ortho Matcher, NE.Transducer, Sentence Splitter, Gazetteer, English Tokenizer, and Document Reset PR to recognize named entities within the text. GATE annotates the location of the crime from the text, using the 'Organization' token for the High Court location.
- IPC section numbers are annotated with the 'Identifier' token, and dates are annotated with the 'Date' token. The information extracted from the corpus is supplemented by creating triplets in the format <(location), (IPC-section number), (date)>.

2.2.3 Semantic Search:

In this phase, the extracted information is stored in a database, enabling the execution of relevant queries to obtain the desired results. Triplets are stored in a MySQL database, enabling data retrieval.

2.2.4 Visualization Analysis and Clustering Analysis:

- Visualization Analysis: R, a language and environment for statistical computing and graphics, is used for visualization. R was chosen due to its free and open-source nature.
- Clustering Analysis: Cluster analysis is effective for quickly reviewing data, especially when there are multiple categories. Clustering is applied to a set of judgments, with the chosen variable being the location of the crime mentioned in the text.

2.3 VLA:

2.3.1 Virtual Legal Assistance Components:

- Consists of four components for legal consultations with an AI-based Virtual Assistant.
- Aim to streamline the legal case journey by providing intelligent access to historical case data.
- Reduces time-consuming manual research efforts by legal experts.

2.3.2 User Interaction and Case Refinement:

- Allows users to add case details, narrowing down the search and ranking references.
- Uses scoring algorithms like RP-score and Mean Reciprocal Rank for reference ranking.
- Recalculates scores upon changes in the case text, guiding legal experts in decision-making.

2.3.3 VLA Architecture:

- Text Analytics: Involves tokenization, cleaning, stop word removal, stemming, and part-of-speech tagging. Utilizes algorithms like Word2vec and Doc2vec for text similarities.
- Knowledge Base: Repository storing domain corpus, rules, rank scores, and trained model information.
- Question Generation Engine: Utilizes semantic networks and ontologies to transform contextual text into interrogative sentences post-content determination.
- User Interface with Dialect Converter: Allows speech-to-text and vice-versa conversions, backed by the Question Generation Engine.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Large Language Model Meta AI (Llama)

1. Initialization and Setup:

- Import necessary modules and libraries for natural language processing and model implementation.
- Define global variables for storing model parameters and configurations.
- Set up functions for data loading, preprocessing, and response generation.

2. Data Loading and Preprocessing:

- Load legal documents and relevant text data into the system.
- Preprocess the text data by tokenizing, normalizing, and encoding it for model input.

3. Model Loading and Initialization:

- Load the Llama model for legal chatbot development.
- Initialize the model and set up the question-answering (QA) bot for handling user queries.

4. User Interaction:

- Receive user queries or messages as input to the chatbot.
- Pass the user input to the QA bot for processing and response generation.

5. Response Generation:

- Utilize the Llama model to generate responses based on the user query.
- Retrieve relevant information from the legal documents and knowledge base to provide accurate answers.

6. *Postprocessing and Output:*

- Postprocess the generated response to ensure readability and coherence.
- Display the final answer to the user along with any relevant sources or references.
- This algorithm outlines the key steps involved in developing a legal chatbot using the Llama model, focusing on data processing, model utilization, user interaction, and response generation. It emphasizes the importance of accurate legal information retrieval and user-friendly output presentation in the chatbot's functionality.

IV. DATASET

1. Event_Summarycongress17.
2. Cybercrime Policies and Legislation In The Pacific.
3. Cyber Crime Investigations.
4. Cyberspace, Cybersecurity, And Cybercrime.
5. Combatting Cybercrime and Cyberterrorism_ Challenges, Trends and Priorities.
6. The Constitution of India.
7. Cyber Laws Overview.
8. A People's Constitution_ The Everyday Life Of Law In The Indian Republic.
9. Practice-Areas_ Cybersecurity-Laws-And-Regulations_India.
10. Cybersecurity Essentials.

V. METHODOLOGY

Fig 1: Data Flow Diagram

1. *Document Data Collection:*

- Gather legal documents relevant to the chatbot's domain, such as contracts, case law, statutes, etc.
- Organize the documents in a structured format for easy retrieval and processing.

2. Preprocessing:

- Tokenize and normalize the text data from the legal documents.
- Remove stopwords, punctuation, and perform any necessary text cleaning steps.
- Optionally, apply advanced preprocessing techniques like lemmatization or named entity recognition (NER).

3. Embedding Model (Sentence Transformers):

- Utilize the Sentence Transformers library (specifically the all-mini-l6-v2 model) to generate embeddings for the preprocessed text data.
- Fine-tune the Sentence Transformers model if needed based on your specific domain or dataset.

4. Vector Database/Indexing (Faiss):

- Set up Faiss, a library for efficient similarity search and clustering of dense vectors.
- Create a Faiss index (index.faiss) to store the embeddings generated by Sentence Transformers.
- Serialize and store additional metadata or mappings in a pickle file (index.pkl) for fast retrieval.

5. User Interaction:

- Develop a user interface (UI) where users can input their legal queries or prompts.
- Implement a mechanism to receive user input and transmit it to the backend for processing.

6. Processing User Input:

- Upon receiving user input through the UI, preprocess the input text similarly to the document data preprocessing step.
- Generate embeddings for the user input using the same Sentence Transformers model.

7. Search and Retrieval (Faiss CPU):

- Use the Faiss CPU version to efficiently search the Faiss index based on the embeddings of the user input.
- Retrieve top-k most similar documents or embeddings from the Faiss index based on cosine similarity or other distance metrics.

8. Response Generation (Llama):

- Retrieve the relevant legal documents or information based on the Faiss search results.
- Pass the retrieved data and user input to the Llama model for response generation.
- Post-process the model's response for readability and coherence before presenting it to the user.

9. Display Response:

- Present the generated response from the Llama model back to the user through the UI.
- Include any relevant information or references along with the response.

VI. RESULTS

Fig 2: Launch Page

Fig 3: User Registration

Fig 4: User Login

Fig 5: Chatbot

Fig 6: Chatbot Query

Fig 7: Extra Functionalities

The result analysis of response times for cybercrime queries indicates a clear correlation between query length and the time taken to provide a comprehensive answer. Short, focused queries received quicker responses, with one-word queries averaging around 49.847 seconds. In contrast, very long queries required significantly more time, averaging approximately 181.858 seconds. This suggests that concise and specific inquiries lead to more efficient and timely assistance in addressing cybercrime-related concerns. Understanding the impact of query length on response times can help streamline communication processes and enhance the effectiveness of providing legal guidance and support in cybercrime investigations.

Fig 9: Performance Analysis of Chatbot

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, this present study has provided a comprehensive overview of various AI-driven solutions that are revolutionizing the legal industry. From contract analysis to legal research and information extraction, these technologies are enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making for legal professionals

Future work in the realm of AI-driven solutions for the legal industry focuses on enhancing lawyer connection platforms and implementing more robust case tracking systems. By leveraging AI algorithms to match clients with lawyers based on their specific needs and preferences, lawyer connection platforms could streamline the process of finding legal representation. Additionally, advanced case tracking systems powered by AI could provide real-time updates on case progress, deadlines, and relevant legal precedents, improving transparency and efficiency in legal proceedings. These advancements hold the potential to further optimize legal services and facilitate smoother interactions between legal professionals and clients.

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